

Structural aspects of complexes of Rh^{III} and Pd^{II} with hexamethylenedibiguanide (C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀)

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Abstract : Complexes of Rh^{III} and Pd^{II} with hexamethylenedibiguanide {hm(BigH⁺)₂} of composition [Rh{hm(BigH⁺)₂}X₂].XH₂O and [Pd₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}X₄] (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻ or NCS⁻); [Pd{hm(BigH⁺)₂}.Cl₂] and [Rh₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}₃].X₆nH₂O (X = OH⁻ or 1/2 SO₄²⁻) and {hm(BigH⁺)₂} = C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀) have been prepared and characterized from the studies of IR, UV, electrical conductance and magnetic susceptibility measurements. Both Rh^{III} and Pd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic suggesting low spin octahedral structure of Rh^{III} and four coordinated square planar geometry of Pd^{II}.

Keywords : Rhodium(III), palladium(II).

Hexamethylenedibiguanide sulphate {hm(BigH₂⁺)₂}.SO₄.H₂O (Fig. A) is a quadridentate chelating molecule and its complexes with some bivalent metal ions are known¹.

Fig. A

The ligand has been found to coordinate with N(2) and N(4) of the both biguanide substituent forming usual six membered chelate rings with metal atoms from each biguanide unit. The coordination complexes of a number of biguanides with various metal ions have been investigated extensively^{2,3}.

The detailed studies on structural aspects of quadridentate biguanides with platinum metals are lacking. To investigate chelating behaviour of quadridentate biguanide, we have prepared and characterized the complexes of Rh^{III} and Pd^{II} with hexamethylenedibiguanide (C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀).

Results and discussion

The acidic solution of RhCl₃(aq) (pH 1–2) reacts with hexamethylenedibiguanide hydrochloride, [hm(BigH₂⁺)₂], forming brick red precipitate {hm(BigH₂⁺)₂}.[RhCl₅.H₂O].

The aqueous suspension of complex salt undergoes halide replacement reaction when refluxed on steam bath forming [Rh.{hm(BigH⁺)₂}.Cl₂].Cl.H₂O as cream yellow product.

The dichloro complex [Rh{hm(BigH⁺)₂}.Cl₂].Cl.H₂O undergoes chloride substitution reactions with potassium salt of appropriate anions, KBr, KI or KNCS forming diacido complexes [Rh{hm(BigH⁺)₂}X₂.X.nH₂O [where X = Br⁻, I⁻ or NCS⁻].

The diacido complexes [Rh{hm(BigH⁺)₂}X₂].X.nH₂O are slightly soluble in hot water but dissolve appreciably in DMF. The DMF solutions of complexes at room temperature (30–31 °C) display electrical conductance value in the range of 65–75 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm² indicating them to be 1 : 1 electrolytes⁴.

An aqueous acidic solutions of Pd^{II} chloride (pH 2–4) reacts with hexamethylenedibiguanide hydrochloride {hm(BigH₂⁺)₂} and gradually forms cream yellow insoluble dinuclear product [Pd₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}.Cl₄]. The anion substitution reaction with KBr, KI or KNCS from chloro complex, [Pd₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}.Cl₄], at reflux temperature gave light to deep yellow complexes [Pd₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}.X₄] (where X = Br, I⁻ or NCS⁻).

All acido complexes of Pd^{II} are sparingly soluble in water but dissolve slightly in DMF yielding feebly conducting solution supporting anions to be coordinated in these

complexes. The insolubility of the complexes indicated their polymeric structure.

In feebly acidic or neutral solution (pH 4–6) the N(5) nitrogen of $\{\text{hm}(\text{BigH}_2^+)\}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4$ (Fig. A) is deprotonated and forms mononuclear complex $[\text{Pd}\{\text{hm}(\text{BigH}^+)\}_2] \cdot \text{SO}_4$ with Pd^{II} and dinuclear complex $[\text{Rh}_2\{\text{hm}(\text{BigH}^+)\}_3] \cdot (\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and Rh^{III} as cream white sparingly soluble salt.

The complex base $[\text{Rh}_2\{\text{hm}(\text{BigH}^+)\}_3] \cdot (\text{OH})_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is obtained at pH 7–8 on refluxing the complex sulphate in basic medium.

The complex chlorides are obtained by refluxing the complex base with dilute HCl. The complex salts are feebly soluble in hot water and qualitative values of electrical conductivity indicated ionic nature of chloride or sulphate ion in both Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes⁴.

Both Rh^{III} and Pd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic suggesting low spin octahedral structure of Rh^{III} and four coordinated square planar geometry of Pd^{II} .

The electronic absorption spectra of Pd^{II} complexes in DMF solutions display medium band in the range of 360–410 nm and strong absorption below 320 nm. The broad band in the visible region (360–410 nm) is attributed to $A_{1g} \rightarrow B_{1g}$ transition in planar ligand field⁵. The strong absorption below 320 nm is attributed to charge transfer transition in complexes.

The electronic absorption spectra of Rh^{III} complex $[\text{Rh}_2\{\text{hm}(\text{BigH}^+)\}_3] \cdot (\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and diacido complexes $[\text{Rh}\{\text{hm}(\text{BigH}^+)\}_2] \text{X}_2 \cdot \text{X} \cdot \text{nH}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- or NCS^-) in DMF solutions display a medium band or shoulder at 320–345 nm attributable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ transition.

The iodo complex displays a broad and strong band at 490 nm and a shoulder near 390 nm attributed to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ transition respectively⁶. At lower wavelength (higher energy) the complexes show strong absorption attributable to charge transfer transition in these complexes.

The IR spectra of complexes display $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NH}_2)$ vibrations as broad band near 3250–3320 cm^{-1} and $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ vibration around 1660–1680 cm^{-1} ⁷. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\delta(\text{NH})$ bands are observed in the range of 1520–1560 cm^{-1} as medium and broad bands⁸. These IR vibrations are broad and strong in free ligand hydrochloride while well resolved in complexes indicating less hydrogen bonding in coordinated ligand molecule. The complex sulphate $[\text{Rh}_2\{\text{hm}(\text{BigH}^+)\}_3] \cdot (\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ displays a broad band at 1150 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu_3(\text{SO}_4)$ vibration of uncoordinated SO_4 (sulphate) group⁹.

In case of dihalo complexes of Rh^{III} and Pd^{II} , the IR spectra of complexes are not well resolved in far infrared region hence no definite band position of (M-X) stretching vibration could be ascertained. The IR spectrum of dithiocyanato complex $[\text{Pd}_2\{\text{hm}(\text{BigH}^+)\}_2] \cdot (\text{SCN}^-)_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ displays a strong and sharp band at 2095 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{NCS})$ and medium band at 720 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{CS})$ and $\delta(\text{NCS})$ at 420 cm^{-1} suggesting sulphur bonded thiocyanate group in $[\text{Pd}_2\{\text{hm}(\text{BigH}^+)\}_2] \cdot (\text{SCN}^-)_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ¹⁰. The broad band at 3450 cm^{-1} and absence of $\rho_{\text{w}}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ near 650–840 cm^{-1} indicated presence of lattice water in the complex.

The IR spectra of $[\text{Rh}\{\text{hm}(\text{BigH}^+)\}_2] \cdot (\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{NCS} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ display a broad and strong band at 2090 cm^{-1} and a weak band at 2005 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(\text{NCS})$ vibration of coordinated as well as ionic thiocyanate group in the complex. The weaker band observed at 820 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu(\text{CS})$ and medium band at 520 cm^{-1} attributable to $\delta(\text{NCS})$ suggested the presence of N-bonded isothiocyanate group in rhodium(III) complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{hm}(\text{BigH}^+)\}_2] \cdot (\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{NCS} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by the reported method¹.

Preparation of the complexes :

Hexamethylenedibiguanidiniumbismono-aquapentachlororhodium(III) hexahydrate :

The aquapentachloro complex salt of hexamethylenedibiguanide was obtained in strongly acidic solution of rhodium(III) chloride. About 0.5 g of rhodium(III) chloride was dissolved in 25 ml 2 N hydrochloric acid and treated with hot aqueous solution of hexamethylenedibiguanidinium chloride (1 : 1 molar ratio), when a brick red product separated immediately. The product was digested for 15 min and collected on a filter. It was washed with water, ethanol and finally dried in air.

The aquapentachloro complex salt is insoluble in ethanol and organic solvents. In hot water it slowly dissolves giving dichloro complex.

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Rh, 20.65 (20.74); N, 13.99 (14.09); Cl, 35.69 (35.75); C, 11.99 (12.08); H, 4.28 (4.43); H_2O , 14.54 (14.50).

cis-Dichlorohexamethylenedibiguanidiniumrhodium(III) chloride :

About 0.4 g pentachloro complex salt; $[\{\text{hm}(\text{BigH}_2^+)\}_2]$.

[RhCl₃.H₂O].6H₂O was suspended in 25 ml water and refluxed for two to three hours. The refluxate was filtered hot and was concentrated to 8–10 ml, when the cream colored product separated. The complex was collected on a filter, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over CaCl₂.

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Rh, 20.81 (20.87); N, 28.01 (28.36); Cl, 21.32 (21.58); C, 24.12 (24.30); H, 4.90 (4.86)

cis-Diacidohexamethylenedibiguanidiniumrhodium(III) anions :

[Rh{hm(BigH⁺)₂}X₂]_nX (X = Br⁻, I⁻ or NCS⁻).nH₂O (n = 0 or 2) :

About 0.4 g dichloro complex was suspended in 30–40 ml water and refluxed with 2.0 g potassium salt of appropriate anion for three to four hours. The refluxate was concentrated to 10–15 ml when cream yellow product separated. The products were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over CaCl₂.

[Rh{hm(BigH⁺)₂}Br₂].Br :

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Rh, 16.15 (16.42); N, 22.10 (22.32); Br, 38.19 (38.28); C, 19.00 (19.13); H, 3.90 (3.82).

[Rh{hm(BigH⁺)₂}I₂].I :

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Rh, 13.35 (13.41); N, 17.99 (18.23); I, 49.39 (49.61); C, 15.41 (15.62); H, 3.08 (3.12).

[Rh{hm(BigH⁺)₂}(NCS)₂].NCS.2H₂O :

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Rh, 17.01 (17.25); N, 30.25 (30.48); C, 26.00 (26.13); H, 4.72 (4.69); H₂O, 6.04 (6.03).

tris-Hexamethylenedibiguanidiniumdirhodium(III) hydroxide tetrahydrate :

[Rh₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}₃](OH)₆.4H₂O :

About 0.8 g of the ligand sulphate was dissolved in 25–30 ml (N) sodium hydroxide solution and was treated with an aqueous solution of RhCl₃(aq) (0.2 g in 25 ml N/10 HCl). The resulting mixture was refluxed for one hour when a dull cream white precipitate separated. The product was thoroughly washed with water and ethanol. It was dried over CaCl₂.

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Rh, 16.64 (16.72); N, 33.90 (34.09); C, 29.01 (29.22); H, 7.01 (6.98); H₂O, 5.67 (5.84).

tris-Hexamethylenedibiguanidiniumdirhodium(III) sulphate tetrahydrate :

[Rh₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}₃](SO₄)₃.4H₂O :

The above complex base [Rh₂hm{BigH⁺}₂].(OH)₆.4H₂O was suspended in dilute H₂SO₄ (N/2) and digested for half an hour when cream white product separated. The

product was washed with water and ethanol and finally dried over CaCl₂.

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Rh, 16.71 (16.80); N, 34.16 (34.25); SO₄, 7.79 (7.83); C, 29.08 (29.36); H, 6.48 (6.52); H₂O, 5.81 (5.87).

Tetrachlorohexamethylenedibiguanidiniumdipalladium(II) :

[Pd₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}Cl₄] :

An aqueous acidic solution of palladium(II) chloride {0.01 mole in 30 ml (0.1 N) HCl} was refluxed with an aqueous solution of hexamethylenedibiguanidinium chloride (0.05 mol in 30–40 ml water) for 20–30 min, when cream yellow product separated. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over CaCl₂.

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Pd, 33.10 (33.22); N, 22.29 (21.94); Cl, 22.05 (22.25); C, 18.78 (18.88); H, 3.80 (3.76).

Tetraacidohexamethylenedibiguanidiniumdipalladium(II) :

[Pd₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}X₄] (X = Br⁻, I⁻ or NCS⁻) :

About 0.4 g tetrachloro complex was suspended in 30–40 ml of water and refluxed with 2.0 g potassium salt of appropriate anion for two hours and resulting products were collected on a filter.

[Pd₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}Br₄] :

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Pd, 25.90 (25.98); N, 17.00 (17.15); Br, 39.00 (39.21); C, 14.60 (14.70); H, 3.10 (2.94).

[Pd₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}I₄] :

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Pd, 21.00 (21.11); N, 13.90 (13.94); I, 50.49 (50.59).

[Pd₂{hm(BigH⁺)₂}(NCS)₄].2H₂O :

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Pd, 27.70 (27.74); N, 25.40 (25.65); C, 21.90 (21.98); H, 3.70 (3.66); H₂O, 4.68 (4.71).

Hexamethylenedibiguanidiniumpalladium(II) chloride :

[Pd{hm(BigH⁺)₂}]Cl₂ :

An aqueous alkaline solution of hexamethylenedibiguanide hydrochloride (0.8 g in 30 ml 0.5 N NaOH) was mixed to 0.4 g of an aqueous acidic solution of palladium(II) chloride. The mixture was acidified with dilute HCl and digested on a steam bath for 30 min when dull white product separated. It was filtered washed and dried in a desiccator over CaCl₂.

Anal : Found (Calcd.) Pd, 23.18 (23.45); N, 30.10 (30.32); Cl, 15.11 (15.35).

The electrical conductance values of aqueous or DMF solution of complexes were qualitatively determined at room temperature. The electronic absorption spectrum of

Note

complexes were recorded on Hilger and Watt H-700 spectrophotometer in DMF or water. The reflectance spectra were recorded using MgCO_3 as standard. The IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 577 and 221 spectrophotometer in KBr disc at CDRI, Lucknow.

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